

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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Abstract: The thesis describes some difficulties in teaching and learning and suggests the ways of avoiding and tackling them considering the effective and productive contemporary methods in teaching the English language.

Keywords: incompatibility, teacher incompetence, grammar, motivation, self study, Matrix methods.

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The relevance of this topic is due to the fact that today more and more teachers note certain problems in learning English and mastering the material. Students often cite language inability in such situations. But there are times when a person knows one or even two languages, however, is not able to master the third. In this case, the cause may be the teaching methodology or the incompatibility of the student and teacher at the psychological level. This situation can be a serious obstacle to learning a language. English, although it is a simple language for learning, is actually not always easy to learn. Difficulties in each case can be caused by different reasons, but in this thesis I would like to list the most common

First mistake. Thinking in the native language. It is found in almost everyone who begins to learn a language, and even those who have been teaching it for a long time. The bottom line is that a person thinks in his native language, translating it into a foreign language.

The second mistake. Teacher incompetence. This may include inefficient presentation of the material, incorrect pronunciation and accent. Often, English teachers at schools and universities know the language at the level of a linguist-scientist, but speak with an emphasis that students adopt from the very first lessons. Learning / talking with native speakers will help to avoid this error.

The third mistake. Criticism towards oneself. Setting the bar high and striving to achieve results as soon as possible is the right way to failure. Subsequently, the student's desire to learn a language disappears, and he considers himself one of those to whom languages are not given. Setting the goal of learning to speak fluently and competently is the right goal, but you need to understand that the results will not be instant.

The fourth mistake. Extreme emphasis on grammar. Such an approach can be either a teacher's mistake or a student's mistake, who decided that language learning is based on grammar. In fact, memorizing the rules will do little if a person is not able to perceive speech

by ear, does not know how to speak a foreign language at all. The process of learning grammar should not be isolated from other processes of learning a language, since exclusively "technical" knowledge of a subject does not contribute to speaking in a foreign language, overcoming the barrier.

The fifth mistake. Weak motivation. If a person undertakes to learn a language under the threat of dismissal or in connection with possible job privileges, this is not the strongest motivation, since certain circumstances prompt him to study, and not his own desire. In this case, there is no involvement in the learning process, it is uninteresting and the brain subconsciously resists receiving new information.

Sixth mistake. Neglect of self-study. Many people are sure that it is enough to turn to a good professional, and he will teach them how to speak. For their part, they consider it quite sufficient to attend classes and be diligent students. But in practice this is not enough. Without constant self-education (and this includes watching films in English, reading literature, and studying various features of the language, slang, etc.), knowledge of English does not rise to the proper level. Again – without interest and full devotion to the subject, the result will be minimal.

In conclusion – popular methods of teaching English:

1. Standard. Most common in schools and universities, despite the fact that it shows low efficiency in comparison with other teaching methods. This technique is a program that is crammed with mostly grammar work. The basis of training is the implementation of exercises based on learned rules. As a rule, it is not easy for pupils to speak and understand by ear.

2. The methodology of studying with native speakers. As noted above, this technique helps students avoid typical pronunciation errors and not adopt the accent of a non-native language teacher. But when communicating with a person of a different language environment, attention is concentrated on establishing contact with him, mental activity is aimed at listening to the words of the teacher, trying to understand him (which at first can be very difficult).

3. Matrix method. To date, the most effective teaching methodology. The essence of this approach is that, first of all, a person must learn to perceive a foreign language by ear (just like children learn a language without knowing the rules of grammar). To this end, the program includes listening to dialogues and texts in English, which the creator called the matrix. Experts call the matrix teaching method revolutionary in learning English, as it is based on the subconscious abilities of a person and the learning process is easy and interesting.

Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that very many people face difficulties in learning English, the main thing is to continue training, not to throw halfway and the result will not be long in coming.

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